

**STRESS AND TIME MANAGEMENT AMONG THE POST GRADUATE
STUDENTS IN KHAMMAM DISTRICT, TELANGANA – A STUDY**

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Stress is common amongst students. You will still encounter unexpected troubles that will rock your sanity. Students entering colleges are at an obvious turning point in their educational career. It is also a crucial phase in their life in which seeds for their future are sown. The time span spent at this stage by them is both psychologically and sociologically a very important period of his life. This period of adolescence has been described as a time of 'Storm and Stress' as many physical and psychological changes take place in the personality of the student. Moreover it is a period of changes in Biological, Cognitive, Social and effective functioning. Puberty involves dramatic endocrine changes that affect the internal and external structures and functioning of the body. These biological changes may be negative or they may be positive opportunities for adaptation depending primarily on how they perceive the changes. It is a period of cognitive development where young people develop the capacity to think about thinking and youth turn to others who are similar to themselves to determine appropriate behavior. In other words, peers increase in importance and to avoid social ridicule, most youth develop uniformity in appearance and behavior. They are also ambitious by nature. They may have so many aspirations and desires to be fulfilled. Despite their best planning and efforts they may not get the desired success. At times they find themselves in a state of utter confusion and bewilderment. Adolescence is a dangerous period of time where young people experience self organization and role confusion. For them, stress mainly comes from academic tests, interpersonal relations, relationship problems,

life changes, and career exploration. Such stress may usually cause psychological, physical and behavioral problems.

Time Management of College Students:

Students' time is a limited resource. Like other limited resources time needs to be effectively managed. Students often have a large number of information processing tasks to do and the task are of different lengths, complexity, priority, deadlines and proneness to Interruptions.

In short P .G students are over loaded by academic work. Students enter the college life with different knowledge, skills or abilities and under fixed time conditions. These differences are translated into differences in achievement. In such circumstances it would be natural for students to consider how they might manage their time effectively. Students often enter higher education from situations where their work routines were more or less prescribed for them by teachers and tutors. Many find that in higher education, the requirements are very difficult and difficult to manage their own time. If there is a continual failure to manage time, an individual may begin to question his competence and will experience strong feelings of stress.

Significance of the Study:

Stress is one of the most serious problems faced by many learners. When students are aware of the reasons for experiencing stress and stress reactions they may learn to adopt appropriate stress management strategies. Hence it becomes necessary to ' understand the stressors which confront our college students, weed them out and do the needful in order to help our learners to be free of the negative effects of stress.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To find out the extent of stress experienced by college students
2. To identify the causes for stress in college students
3. To find out the stress management strategies of college students
4. To find out the time management practices of college students.

Research methodology:

The study was conducted among The Post graduate students of khammam town, Telangana state. Survey questionnaire was distributed to whole town of 60 students. The survey also included. Different coping strategies, as used by the students. The survey included questions to explore factors causing stress to the students and their expectations from the faculty. Convenience sampling method was used for data collection. Various methods are used to analyses data, weighted average, and Percentage Method.

Limitations of the study:

The study was conducted post graduate students in khammam only, who were pursuing their studies in different streams namely Sciences Humanities and Commerce Mgt were selected. They were in between the age 18- 24 years.

Review of Literature:

The review examines first the prevalence of stress among the P G college students. An elaborate review of the etiology of stress is presented with stressors classified into academic and non-academic stressors. Studies on time management practices of college students are also reviewed.

Stress among Learners:

The first step in tackling stress is to acknowledge its existence among learners. Peterson's (1982) investigation of stress among adolescent students, revealed that students experienced moderate level of stress associated with school, college related events and circumstances. Ramamurthy (1983) conducted a normative and limited survey of post graduate students. Five questions were developed and an objective report was required. Their results indicate that students who were listed under normal mental health group were experiencing stress. The investigation by Dobson and Allar (1983) reveals that over 66 percent of the students felt that they had experienced a lot of stress, only four percent reported 'No stress'.

Munson-Cariton (1984) has reported the results of his investigation of graduate students, based on an analysis of data. He stated that more students were experiencing symptom of stress.

Price, Jurs, Michael Rhonehouse and Isham (1985) concluded that students who were their samples, reported high levels of stress. Anderson Gail kurin (1986) designed six models of stress and found majority of students experiencing high stress and depression. Madre and John Blair (1988) found students experiencing moderate stress.

Factors affecting stress /Environmental stressors:

- 1, Peers treating freshers unlike the way treat each other.
- 2, Faculty treating different peer groups differently.
- 3, Need to mingle with peers of different race/ethnicity on campus.
- 4, Finding support groups sensitive to specific needs.
- 5, Living in the local community.
- 6, Adjusting to the campus environment.
- 7, Participating in class.
- 8, Meeting with faculty

Academic stressors

- 1, Handling the academic workload .
- 2, Meeting deadlines for course assignments.
- 3, Fear of failing to meet program expectations.
- 4, Fulfilling responsibilities at home and school.
- 5, Taking exams, Handling relationships and Writing papers.

Monetary Stressors:

- 1, Family having money problems.
- 2, Paying monthly expenses
- 3, Arranging childcare.
- 4, Being obligated to participate in family functions

Physical Stressors:

- 1, Sleep disorder.
- 2, Poor diet.
- 3, Drug misuse.
- 4, Alcohol misuse.

- 5, Excess heat.
- 6, Excess caffeine.
- 7, Excess cold.
- 8, Illness Smoking.
- 9, Lack of relaxation.
- 10, Chronic fatigue

Psychological Stressors:

- 1, Peer pressure.
- 2, Excess anger.
- 3, Unrealistic beliefs .
- 4, Health worries
- 5, Unrealistic expectations.
- 6, Excessive worrying.
- 7, Unhappy childhood .
- 8, Unemployment
- 9, Perfectionism.
- 10, Loneliness.
- 11, Low self esteem.
- 12, People pleasing .
- 13, Negative self-talk .
- 14, Personality.
- 15, Right thinking style.
- 16, Excessive self-criticism.
- 17, Exam pressure

Stress consequences:

Physical Symptoms

- 1, Shallow, rapid breathing.
- 2, Increased muscle tension and heart rate
- 3, Headaches.
- 4, Stomach upsets.

5, Sleep disturbances

6, Appetite changes Behavioral Signs 1, Feeling anxious, depressed or irritable 2, Being overly sarcastic or flippant

Cognitive Signs

When you feel stress, hormones including adrenaline and cortisol flood the body, causing:

1. The body's need for oxygen to increase.
- 2, Heart rate and blood pressure to go up
3. Blood vessels in the skin to constrict.
4. Muscles to tense
5. Blood sugar level to increase.
6. Blood to have an increased tendency to clot
7. The body's cells to pour stored fat into the bloodstream

Prolonged stress can take a terrible toll on your physical and emotional health, as well as on your relationships. This is especially true if you don't have an outlet through which to release anxiety. Chronic depression and anxiety have been linked to other physical problems and conditions, such as

Time management 10 better ways and less stress:

1. Trash perfectionism 2. Beat procrastination 3. Set priorities 4. Work backwards
5. Keep a time log 6. Learn to say no 7. Use time saving techniques 8. Find creative solutions 9. Multitasking vs multi-focusing 10. Work in intervals

Stress controlling strategies:

Controlling the stress in your life and learning how you react to it are important. By incorporating the following simple stress-busting techniques into your daily routine, you can learn how to break free from anxiety-ridden thoughts and behaviors.

1. Keep a stress journal. One of the first steps in managing stress is to identify situations, experiences or people that tend to trigger tension or worry. Once you do this, you can figure out how to reduce these stressors.
2. Learn relaxation exercises, including deep breathing, muscle relaxation, stretching,

visualization and meditation.

3. Avoid drinking too much caffeine, which can increase feelings of anxiety and agitation.
- 4 Get enough sleep.
5. Eat a nutritious diet and exercise regularly. Not only will this prepare your body to withstand the physical effects of stress, but it will also strengthen your mind to cope with stress and stay on an even keel.
6. Try to stay on top of your schoolwork as a way of decreasing your overall stress and worry.
7. Forget perfection. Talk about pressure! Learn to feel good about doing the best you can.
8. Make the most of a busy schedule but don't go overboard. Many college students take on too many activities and find it hard to keep up with everything.
9. Take breaks to reenergize and gain perspective. De-stress by listening to music, talking with a friend, reading a magazine that help you relax.
10. Seek help. Talk about the stress in your life with your health care professional.
11. Build a network of friends who can help you cope in a positive way. In talking with Friends, you'll most likely find out that they also feel overwhelmed from time to time.

Survey analysis:

Table –No.01. Respondents Gender wise distribution of students

Gender	No of Students	%
Male	35	57%
female	25	43%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data

The table-01 is about the gender of people who took part in the survey. A total of 60 respondents were involved, out of this, males took the greater percentage of 57%

and the remaining 43% went for the females. This survey was conducted among selected University level students.

Table – 02. Respondents Subject wise Distribution.

Subjects	No of Students	%
Science	24	40%
Humanities	16	27%
Commerce	20	33%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data

The table - 02 shows the percentage of respondents with regards to their level of subjects. Science greater portion of the table with 39%. they were followed by Humanities with 35%, next was the Commerce and Mgt with 17%. There was a total of 60 respondents.

Table – 03. Respondents College wise Distribution.

Type of College	No of students	%
University colleges	24	39%
Government Colleges	20	34%
Womens colleges	16	26%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data.

The table – 03, the origins of respondent. The highest percentage of 39%, university college. The second was government colleges with 34%, followed by women's college students who both had 26% respectively.

Table – 04. Respondents age wise Distribution.

Age	No of Studens	%
18 – 20	42	70%
20 – 22	13	21%
22 - 24	05	09%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data.

The table-04 shows the age of respondent. Being grouped in age categories the ages of 18 to 20 were much involved in the survey with a percentage of 70%, the ages of 20 to 22 was next with 21% and lastly is the ages from 22 to 24 with 9%.

Table – No.05. Respondents College wise Distribution

Source of stress factor	No of Students	%
Troubles with girls or boys friends	21	40%
Conflicts with parents	11	25%
Problems at rooms	12	35%
Place change	16	80%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data.

The table – 05 explains relationship factors as a source of stress. There were 21 respondents with regards to this chart. Conflicts with parents took the least percentage with 25%, Working with new place had the greatest percentage of 82%. %, followed by troubles with boyfriends and girlfriends with 40%. Room conflicts was next with 35%. In this regard working with new people is a great relationship factor as source of stress.

Table 06. Academic factors as source of Stress wise Distribution

Source of stress	No of Students	%
Class work load	11	18%
Lower grade	05	09%
More hours studies	08	12%
Language skills, problems	07	11%
Procreation	05	09%
Examinations	05	07%
Missing Classes	04	04%
Misunderstanding of lectures	09	14%
Lots of group work	10	16%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data.

The table- 06 shows academic factors as a source of stress, like the previous table, respondents had the option to choose more than one answer. There were total of 60 respondents. The increased class workload (assignments) accounted for the highest percentage which was 18%, followed by lots of group work which was 16%. Frustration due to misunderstanding lectures had a significant impact with 14% which is third on the table. Missing lectures seems to have less impact of stress level of students with a percentage of 4%. Many hours of studies with, language difficulties, lower grades, procreation and fear of examination are significant academic factors that causes stress with percentages of 12%, 11%, 9%,9% and 7% respectively.

Table –07. Environment factors as a source of Stress wise Distribution.

Environment factors of Stress	No of Students	%
No job and quite job	13	21%
Lack of Computer	01	02%
Bad livig	04	06%
Diverce between parants	01	02%
Un familiar situation	02	04%
Future worries	24	40%
Unrealistic expectations	09	15%
Fear	06	10%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data

From the data illustrated by the table - 07 on environmental factors as source of stress, future worries account for the highest percentage of stress to students, thus 40% followed by lack of job 21% and then unrealistic expectations 15%. Students are less affected by the divorce between parents and the lack of computer and the percentage of the two is 2 %. Fear as an environmental factor however causes a significant stress to students which represent 10% of the total respondents. Bad

living condition is the 5th factor followed by students being put in an unfamiliar situation.

Table –08. Personal factors as source of Stress wise Distribution

Source of Personal factors stress	No of Students	%
Financial factors	13	22%
Health problems	08	14%
Poor Eating Habits	05	08%
Combining job with students	04	07%
Changing in living	09	14%
Change in Sleeping Habits	12	20%
New responsibilities	09	15%
Total	60	100

Source: Survey data.

The table – 08, shows the personal factors as a source of stress and the respondents could choose more than one option. We had 60 respondents. Financial difficulties had the biggest percentage of 22%, followed by change in sleeping habits with 14%, new responsibilities came next with 15%, health issues and change in living environments both had 14% making them next and the last two were poor eating habits and combining jobs with studies having 8% and 7% respectively. Financial difficulty happens to get students more stressed up more than any other personal factors.

Findings:

1. Males took the greater percentage of 57% and the remaining 43% went for the females
2. The students 40%. They were followed by Humanities with 27%, next was the Commerce and Mgt with 33%.
3. The highest percentage of 39%, University College. The second was government colleges with 34%,
4. The student age of 18 to 20 were much involved in the survey with a percentage of 70%, the ages of 20 to 22 years, least 9%.of 22-24 years.

5. Conflicts with parents took the least percentage with 25%, Working with new place had the greatest percentage of 82%. %.
6. The increased class workload (assignments) accounted for the highest percentage which was 18%,
7. Frustration due to misunderstanding lectures had a significant impact with 14%.
8. Many hours of studies with, language difficulties, lower grades, procreation and fear of examination are significant academic factors that causes stress with percentages of 12%, 11%, 9%,9% and 7% respectively.
9. The highest percentage of stress to students, thus 40% followed by lack of jobs.
10. The students 21% and then unrealistic expectations 15%. Students are less affected by the divorce between parents and the lack of computer knowledge.
11. Fear as an environmental factor however causes a significant stress to students which represent 10% of the total respondents. Bad living condition is the 5th factor followed by students being put in an unfamiliar situation.
12. Financial difficulties had the biggest percentage of 22%.
13. Responsibilities came next with 15%.

Financial difficulty happens to get students more stressed up more than any other personal factors.

Suggestions:

Emotions are not the only approach to control. While facing stress, they can take a different perspective and learn to cope with it by changing their views. Stress-induced emotions can be self-managed. The management students should learn to express and manage their emotions and to develop positive relations and an optimistic view of life. Pay attention to their physical and mental health and examine their emotions at all times to avoid onset of stress-induced depression or physical disorders. Family support is helpful for students facing stress, while management students should take advantage of family support, their family members should try to understand their interests, specialties, and abilities so as to avoid having too high expectations of them and causing them additional stress. Cultivate an undaunted spirit. Once any stress-induced emotion arises, relax

appropriate channel, examine their own problems, and seek solutions. The importance of healthy diversions , physical workout and discussions with friends, Yoga, cannot be underestimated but unhealthy diversions like movie addiction, cell phone addiction are very harmful and should be avoided. In general , the students must build a positive outlook and a confident self image.

Conclusion:

Sources of stress found out in through the study have a direct relation with the stress level of students. The reasons for stress cannot be limited to these. It varies according to students and their psychology. In conclusion the results of this study are suggestive as to the necessary components of a stress management program specific to the needs of university students. A better approach may be the use of a stress management workshop, specifically geared to the stressors encountered by university students. Certainly, stress in the college setting cannot be eliminated but we can and Students have relatively carefree lives with not much to worry about except for getting assignments in on time, passing exams and getting good place. However, despite the simplicity of its design a lot of students still find it difficult to survive college or university without stress, simply because they have not been taught good time management techniques. It is important that students master this skill to manage their stress levels. Stop stressing yourself out and begin managing your time properly. Good luck!

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